

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

Deliverable D4.1: Preliminary report on the impact of agricultural, climate, environmental and trade policies

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DATE OF APPROVAL: 29.04.2024

APPROVED BY PROJECT COORDINATOR: Marc Muller

DATE OF APPROVAL: 29.04.2024

CALL Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal

WORK PROGRAMME EU agriculture within a safe and just operating space and planetary boundaries
Topic ID HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01-12

PROJECT WEB SITE: <https://brightspace-project.eu/>

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History of changes

Version	Publication date	Changes	Who
0.1	15.04.2024	Draft Version	Paolo Sckokai
0.2	17.04.2024	Internal Review	Olaf Heidelberg
0.3	19.04.2024	Internal Review	Birgit Mueller
0.4	24.04.2024	Internal Review	Anne Maréchal
Final	29.04.2024	Consolidation/Approval	Paolo Sckokai
Final	29.04.2024	Approval	Marc Muller

Citation

Balázs, K. & Cechura, L. & Chakrabarti, A. & Coderoni, S. & Disdier, A. & Krisztin, T. & Meinhart, B. & Kuhn, T. & Muzzillo, M. & Podmaniczky, L. & Sanjuán, A.I. & Sckokai, P. & Varacca, A. (2024). Deliverable D4.1 (D7) Preliminary report on the impact of agricultural, climate, environmental and trade policies. BrightSpace Horizon Europe project, GA Nr. 101060075.

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In this deliverable we have carried out a systematic review of the literature on the relationships between some key public policies affecting agricultural and food and the SJOS dimensions. In general, our results show that the available evidence is somehow scattered across the SJOS thematic areas, with a clear prevalence of the environmental (SOS) with respect to the social (JOS) ones. Thus, there is a clear research gap in exploring the impact of public policies on JOS issues such as social equity, health and nutrition security. Moreover, very few studies explore synergies and trade-offs between different SJOS dimensions. This is especially relevant if one wishes to evaluate a complex policy mix such as the Green Deal of the EU. Finally, from a methodological perspective, the available studies provide some interesting hints for extending the available toolkit for ex-ante policy modelling, which deserve further research.

In addition to the literature review, we have provided a description of the activities that we are planning to carry out during the time span of Work Package 4 (ending in month 36 of the project), emphasising their potential contribution to the modelling activities that are carried out in other WPs.

2. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable presents preliminary work from WP4. The WP aims to analyse and measure the impact of past and current EU policies on the SJOS dimensions for the EU agri-food systems. The WP takes an ex-post perspective in the analysis of policies, but, at the same time, aims to provide some methodological insights for ex-ante policy modelling, which is developed in other WPs of the BrightSpace project. WP4 aims to systematically analyse the available theoretical and empirical knowledge on the relationships between public policies and the SJOS dimensions, identify the most relevant research gaps and carry out some novel empirical analysis, which can provide the basis for the modelling activities carried out in other WPs.

Using the WP1 interpretation of the SJOS as a reference, in this preliminary deliverable we have carried out a systematic review of the literature on the impact of some key agricultural, food and environmental policies on the transition toward a SJOS for EU agri-food systems. The deliverable is structured in three main chapters, which correspond to the three policy areas to be analysed in the three tasks of WP4: (1) CAP policy tools, with a special focus on Agri-Environmental and Climate Measures (*Task 4.1*); (2) EU trade policies, with a special focus on Non-Tariff Measures (*Task 4.2*); and (3) EU climate-related policies that are impacting agri-food systems (*Task 4.3*). Together with the literature review, in each chapter we identify the main research gaps and we provide a description of the empirical analyses we plan to carry out to complete the WP4 activities (i.e. by month 36), discussing also their potential contribution to the ex-ante modelling activities carried out in other WPs.

The description of the intended empirical analysis is the basis for the content of the final WP4 deliverable. However, note that the described activities represent the intention of the work we aim to conduct. The actual activities might slightly deviate from this description depending on the project developments.

3. EX-POST IMPACT OF CAP TOOLS

3.1. Literature review on the existing empirical evidence

In this section, we focus on the studies addressing the ex-post evaluation of the CAP policy instruments relevant to achieving a SJOS for European agriculture. The reviewed papers have been organized into two main groups: (1) studies aimed at addressing the Safe Operating Space (SOS) outcomes (e.g., biodiversity, land use, water use, nutrient flows, chemical pollution, GHG emissions), (2) papers aimed at evaluating the Just Operating Space (JOS) outcomes (e.g., nutrition security, health, labour fairness, social equity, farm resilience). The review begins by identifying the main papers belonging to the first group, emphasizing the most important methodological differences as well as the SOS outcomes analysed and the main implications of the results. A different logic is then applied to the papers that focus on the JOS outcomes. As most empirical investigations reviewed align with the SOS category, and only a minority can be attributed to the JOS group, the studies are only differentiated based on the different outcomes analysed.

The disparity between the number of studies targeted to SOS and JOS outcomes highlights a research gap in the evaluation of the latter within the context of the CAP. Another recurring theme in the literature is the lack of accurate environmental and social data in the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN), which, as we discuss later in this section, represents one of the main problems when addressing topics in the SJOS domain.

3.1.1. SOS Outcomes

The assessment of the CAP's impacts on SOS outcomes has evolved over time, with the use of increasingly advanced and accurate instruments to collect and analyse data. Early research mainly consisted of extensive literature reviews and meta-analyses on Pillar II Agri-Environmental and Climate Measures (AECMs)' impacts, as done by Kleijn and Sutherland (2003), Batàry et al. (2011, 2015), Scheper et al. (2013), and Tuck et al. (2014). Additionally, a few papers employed primary data. These have been collected either through surveys, as done by Primdahl et al. (2003), Armsworth et al. (2012), and Kuhfuss and Subervie (2018), or, more recently, through remote sensing, as in Fugazza et al. (2022) and Michalek et al. (2022). Conversely, a larger stream of literature exploited secondary (farm level) microdata, provided by regional/public administrations, as evidenced in studies by Pufahl and Weiss (2009); Chabé-Ferret and Subervie (2013); Udagawa et al. (2014); Bertoni et al. (2020); Stetter et al. (2022); and Reese et al. (2023). However, the most popular secondary data source has been the Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN), used by Arata and Sckokai (2016); Coderoni and Esposti (2018); Cisilino et al. (2015); Bertoni et al. (2021); Uehleke et al. (2022); Uehleke et al. (2023); Varacca et al. (2023); and Coderoni et al. (2023). Although this database offers harmonized farm statistics that easily allow for cross-country comparisons, indicators for environmental outcomes are still scarce. As such, many studies complement sustainability indicators with other databases and ad-hoc surveys. Moreover, when measuring input use, most researchers are forced to use expenditure data rather than actual quantities. This represents a great limitation to a precise estimate of the effects of the CAP tools on issues like chemical pollution or nutrient flows.

The reviewed studies vary not only in the types of data but also in the methods employed to analyse them. A stream of literature has employed standard econometric techniques. This comprises studies mainly aimed at assessing Pillar II AECMs' effects. However, to mitigate the risk of selection bias potentially introduced by using these standard approaches, another consistent body of work has employed more sophisticated econometric techniques that allowed to account for farm-level characteristics. These studies show a greater variety in the CAP measures taken into consideration. They represent ex-post assessments of the effects of one or more Pillar II AECMs (Pufahl and Weiss, 2009; Udagawa et al., 2014; Arata and Sckokai, 2016; Uehleke et al., 2019; Uehleke et al., 2022; Michalek et al., 2022). The effects of the transition to organic farming, as part of Pillar II, have been explored by Chabé-Ferret and Subervie (2013); Bertoni et al., (2020), and Reese et al. (2023). Additionally, Cisilino et al. (2015) compared the impact between conventional and organic farming. Interestingly, all these studies found positive effects of the conversion to organic in terms of environmental outcomes. Other papers focused on the effects of greening as part of Pillar I (Varacca et al., 2023; Fugazza et al., 2022; Bertoni et al., 2021; Coderoni and Esposti, 2018; Kuhfuss and Subervie, 2018). Finally, Mary (2013) and Coderoni et al. (2023) are the only studies simultaneously focusing on measures from both Pillar I and Pillar II.

From a methodological perspective, most of these studies (Michalek et al., 2022; Bertoni et al., 2020; Arata and Sckokai, 2016; Chabé-Ferret and Subervie, 2013; Pufahl and Weiss, 2009) combine matching algorithms with difference-in-difference (DID) techniques to ensure comparability and mitigate the potential confounding effects from time-invariant unobserved factors. However, the choice of the covariates introduced in the analysis is crucial (Uehleke et al., 2022). Some studies (Arata and Sckokai, 2016; Pufahl and Weiss, 2009), by including the pre-treatment land management measures as covariates, face a bias risk: farms might exhibit lower land management intensity before entering a program due to factors unrelated to participation. To address this issue, some studies employed more advanced matching procedures, such as a combination of Mahalanobis distance, exact matching on entry years, and Kernel matching (Uehleke et al., 2022) or coarsened exact matching (Bertoni et al.,

2020). However, such impact identification only compares the average differences between participants and matched non-participants. This means that only the ATE or ATT (average treatment effect or average treatment effect on the treated) can be measured. To overcome this issue, a very recent stream of literature is employing Machine Learning (ML) techniques to ex-post evaluate the heterogeneous effect of CAP's tools on both environmental and economic indicators. These studies include Coderoni et al. (2023); Uehleke et al. (2023); Stetter et al. (2022); and Bertoni et al. (2021).

This body of literature can be further classified according to the different SOS outcomes analysed: biodiversity, nitrogen and phosphorus loading, land conversion, and climate change.

In the early literature reviews and meta-analyses, biodiversity levels have been primarily measured through species richness and abundance (Kleijn and Sutherland, 2003; Batàry et al. 2011; Scherper et al., 2013; Tuck et al., 2014; Batàry et al., 2015). Most of the studies employing standard econometric techniques also used animal and plant species as indicators, as in Calvi et al., 2018; Fuentes-Montemayor et al., 2012; Armsworth et al., 2012; Kleijn et al., 2006, and Primdahl et al., 2003, or composite nature value indicators, as computed by Desjeux et al., 2015. Among these studies, the biodiversity impact of AECMs has yielded mixed findings. For example, Primdahl et al. (2003); Fuentes-Montemayor et al. (2012); Batàry et al. (2015); and Desjeux et al. (2015) report beneficial effects of AECMs on biodiversity indicators, while negligible or even detrimental effects emerge in Kleijn and Sutherland (2003); Granlund et al. (2005); Bellebaum et al. (2018); Kaligaric et al. (2019) and Calvi et al. (2018). Greater details are provided by Kleijn et al. (2006), who found a more positive impact on the abundance of common species rather than on endangered ones. Relatedly, Armsworth et al. (2012) highlighted the potential threat to biodiversity under overly simplified policy schemes, suggesting that a more complex measure design might result in better environmental outcomes. Conversely, studies using more advanced econometric approaches concentrated on indicators such as livestock numbers (Cisilino et al., 2019) and density (Pufahl and Weiss, 2009) and, foremost, crop heterogeneity (Cisilino et al., 2019; Arata and Sckokai, 2016; Chabé-Ferret and Subervie, 2013; Bertoni et al., 2020). Most of these studies proved that the analysed measures were at least partly effective in improving biodiversity indicators.

In the evaluation of nitrogen and phosphorus loading, researchers have mainly focused on the use of pesticides and fertilizers, as done by Varacca et al. (2023); Uehleke et al. (2023, 2022); Stetter et al. (2022); Kuhfuss and Subervie (2018); Arata and Sckokai (2016); Cisilino et al., 2019; and Pufahl and Weiss (2009). Among these, the studies by Kuhfuss and Subervie (2018) and Cisilino et al. (2019) have been the only ones to directly quantify herbicide and pesticide use respectively, while the rest have primarily employed expenditure data as indirect measures. Furthermore, other papers analysed the area allocated to cover crops for soil nitrate recovery and the length of fertilizer-free grass buffer strips (Chabé-Ferret and Subervie, 2013; Fugazza et al., 2022) or the presence of nitrogen-fixing crops (Bertoni et al., 2021; Fugazza et al., 2022). Also in this case, findings vary across studies. Uehleke et al. (2022) and Uehleke et al. (2023) found that CAP's tools resulted in a moderate decrease in fertilizer expenditures. Similarly, Pufahl and Weiss (2009); Arata and Sckokai (2016), and Kuhfuss and Subervie (2018) showed a positive impact. On the contrary, Bertoni et al. (2021) detected an increase in nitrogen-fixing crops, while Chabé-Ferret and Subervie (2013) found effectiveness for buffer strips but no effects for cover crops. Finally, recent studies from Varacca et al. (2023) and Stetter et al. (2022) found no significant effects.

Great attention has also been dedicated to the effects of CAP on reducing land conversion. This has been measured in different ways. For example, Primdahl et al. (2003) used the share of permanent grassland, abandoned land, and hedges per utilized agricultural area. Similarly, Uehleke et al. (2022); Bertoni et al. (2020); Arata and Sckokai (2016); and Pufahl and Weiss (2009) measured land conversion

in terms of grassland share, while Bertoni et al. (2021) employed fallow land share as an indicator. Regarding the results, all these papers reported positive impacts of CAP tools on the reduction of land conversion.

More recently, several studies in the literature have directly measured GHG emissions to assess the impact of the CAP tools on climate change. These studies include Coderoni et al. (2023), Michalek (2022), Stetter et al. (2022), Bertoni et al. (2021), and Coderoni and Esposti (2018). All these papers detected beneficial effects of the CAP tools in reducing GHG emissions, with the only exception of Stetter et al. (2022), who found no positive impact for participating farms.

Finally, a growing body of literature centred on eco-efficiency (classically defined as the ratio between economic value added and environmental damage) is simultaneously analysing the environmental and economic impact of the measures. Following Baráth et al. (2023), the effects of AECMs on eco-efficiency are mixed, as some found them to be positive (Picazo-Tadeo et al., 2011; Bonfiglio et al., 2017; Eder et al., 2021; Beltrán-Esteve et al., 2012), negligible (Baráth et al., 2023; Godoy-Durán et al., 2017; Ait Sidhoum et al., 2023a,b), or even negative (Stepién et al., 2017; Stetter and Sauer, 2023). The environmental outcomes analysed in the literature are fertilizers and pesticide use, soil conservation, waste management, nutrient balance, GHG emissions, phosphorus, and nitrogen balance. However, also in the context of eco-efficiency studies, FADN's data quality represents a huge constraint to the analysis, as environmental outcomes can only be assessed through indirect measures. As previously mentioned, the database primarily monitors farms' income and economic indicators, such as input expenditures, thus lacking accurate environmental data.

3.1.2. JOS Outcomes

The FADN also lacks variables addressing social themes. This is probably the main explanation for the very limited number of studies in the literature aimed at evaluating the CAP's effects on JOS outcomes. The scarcity of data on social variables, such as health, has been also pointed out by Walls et al. (2016). They recognize this limitation partly stems from the difficulty of collecting data on social indicators, but also from the CAP's primary focus on economic objectives. Consequently, most of the existing studies targeting JOS outcomes have concentrated on the CAP's impact on rural employment and income distribution.

The studies on the effects on rural employment have been systematically reviewed by other recent studies (Lillemets et al., 2022; Vigani et al., 2019; Schuh et al., 2016). Vigani et al. (2019) and Schuh et al. (2016) only focused on those measuring the impact on employment, in terms of migration of workers from the agricultural sector to other industries and creation of rural employment. Conversely, Lillemets et al. (2022) also accounted for other socioeconomic indicators, such as gender equality (in terms of the impact on women's participation in the agricultural sector), which, however, was found to be modest.

Apart from these differences, all three review papers aimed at assessing the heterogeneity of the effects across the two CAP Pillars. Lillemets et al. (2022) found that Pillar I has been more effective in decreasing the labor outflow from agriculture than Pillar II. Using static and dynamic panel data estimators, Olper et al. (2012) also showed the benefits of Pillar I in maintaining labour in agriculture. However, Schuh et al. (2016) and Vigani et al. (2019) suggested that the positive effects differ among Member states and regions. Thus, the effects of CAP tools on agricultural employment seem to largely depend on different market and production structures. This was also suggested by other papers that employed standard econometric approaches (Garrone et al., 2019; Tocco et al., 2013; Psaltopoulos et al., 2006). Notably, Tocco et al. (2013) found a difference in policy response across new and old

member states; in the new countries, both pillars had a positive effect on preventing the exit of labour from agriculture, while in the old ones, no impact was detected. Different results were obtained by Petrick and Zier (2011), who, applying a DID-matching technique, found that investment aids and transfers to less-favoured areas had a zero marginal employment effect in Germany.

Most of Pillar I's direct payments have, among others, the objective of income redistribution. Studies aimed at assessing the effects of direct payments on income disparity are mixed, as some found them to be positive (Keeney, 2000; Severini and Tantari, 2013, 2015; Piet and Desjeux, 2021), negligible (Ciliberti et al., 2022), or even negative, as they increase income concentration (Allanson, 2006; Schmid et al., 2006; El Benni and Finger, 2012).

In general, however, several JOS dimensions (health, nutrition security, farm resilience) have been virtually neglected in the recent literature on the CAP impacts. Inadequate data is very likely to be the main reason, but also the historical economic focus of the CAP. Given the recent widening of the CAP objectives, this is certainly an area that deserves more research attention. In Brightspace, WP3, WP7 and WP8 are going to carry out specific research activities in this area, especially on issues related to health and nutrition.

3.2. Planned empirical work to provide additional empirical evidence

3.2.1. Ex post impact of agri-environmental schemes via ML techniques

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) represents the primary policy instrument of the European Union (EU), at least in terms of budget share. Since the 1992 MacSharry reform, environmental and ecological concerns have become one of the main reasons why EU policymakers have sustained the CAP expenditure over the years. Given that such topics remain highly prioritized in the current political agendas, this subtask aims at estimating the heterogeneous causal effect of the EU agri-environmental measures on several farm-level economic and environmental performance indicators. Our approach makes use of Double Machine Learning (Chernozukov et al., 2018; Knaus, 2022) techniques to deal with selection on observables more reliably, while fully exploiting the extent of information in the European FADN dataset, which we consider our reference dataset. The goal of this sub-task is to produce a scientific publication that addresses the research question discussed above, thereby contributing to the growing literature on the effectiveness of these pillar 2 policy instruments. Additionally, upon aggregating the heterogeneous effects across relevant farm subgroups, the estimated parameters produced by this work will aid in performing sensitivity analysis in larger market models such as IFM-CAP and FARMDYN. The UCSC team will lead the work, potentially collaborating with other partners to be identified.

3.2.2. Ex post impact of organic farming via ML techniques

Much the upcoming CAP programming period will hinge on the 2020 Farm to Fork strategic document (European Commission, 2020). Among the several proposed targets to attain sustainable food production in the EU, encouraging the uptake of organic farming (OF) techniques is certainly one of the most important and controversial ones. Although OF has been part of the EU agricultural systems and, relatedly, of the CAP policy toolbox for a long time, assessing the impact of these practices on either the environment or farmers' profitability remains an important area of research. We tackle this research question by applying staggered difference-in-differences methods to the complete European FADN dataset. Specifically, we develop an extension to the well-known Callaway and Sant'Anna (2021)

estimator where we employ Double Machine Learning techniques to fully exploit the richness of our data. The evaluation covers both farm economic performance and input use indicators. The intended outcome of this sub-task is a scientific publication focussing not only on the causal effects of organic farming, but also on the methodological novelties introduced by the paper. Moreover, the causal estimands addressed in this work will help performing sensitivity analysis in larger market models when calibrating the parameters pertaining to OF. The work is going to be primarily carried out by the UCSC team, potentially collaborating with other partners such as the UNIBO team.

3.2.3. Ex-post impact of low-input agriculture (low fertiliser/pesticide use) via multicrop models

The aim of this task is to develop micro-econometric multi-crop models that can be estimated with FADN data. The intended modelling framework and estimation approaches build on previous work of the involved team (Koutchadé et al, 2018, 2021). The considered models are primarily designed for investigating, through simulation studies, the effects of a wide variety of policies aimed to reduce uses of agrochemicals (e.g., Carpentier et al, 2023). These models of crop production choices – target yield levels, uses of pesticides and fertilizers, and acreages – account for (i) null acreage choices based on a consistent micro-economic framework and (ii) farmers’ and farms’ unobserved heterogeneity based on random farm-specific parameters.

Their structure is that of quadratic Positive Mathematical Programming (PMP) models. Their estimation is based on the well-known Karush-Kuhn-Tucker optimality conditions, which enable us to consider data involving numerous production regimes. Although these models are initially based on standard crop level dual input demand and yield supply models as in Koutchadé et al (2018), models based on (approximate) crop level discrete crop production practice choices will also be considered. The estimation and calibration procedures developed in this task will be usable for practitioners developing quadratic PMP models, especially those interested in farm-level models. The model estimated in this task can also deliver farm-level elasticity parameters that can be used for calibrating mathematical programming models.

3.2.4. Ex-post evaluation of greening payment and LFA payments

We propose to implement three studies to assess the effect of green payments and LFA payments on economic and environmental outcomes. The first two studies focus on the effect of grassland conservation measures (LFA reform), while the third one examines the impact of diversification introduced in green payments.

In the first study we investigate the impact of an exogenous source of income support variation related to Less Favoured Areas (LFA) and the grassland premium on farms’ technical efficiency (TE), environmental efficiency (EE), and grassland conservation in France. We exploit a CAP reform, as a natural experiment, which affects three groups of farms differently. By using a DID-IPW strategy, we compare farms that benefited from an increase in LFA payments to farms that did not experience a change. We also compare farms that suffered from the loss of the grassland premium to neutral farms.

In the second study, we examine the long-term impact of the Least Favoured Mountain Areas Policy both on farm demography, agricultural employment and local spillover/multiplier effects on rural employment. We use two identification strategy. Firstly, we exploit the political alignment of the “députés” in 1961 with the national government as a quasi-experimental variation of the probability to benefit from the policy for a municipality. Secondly, we use the staggered design of LFA eligibility.

The third study assesses the effect of the green payments on farm economic and environmental performances. By combining Regression Discontinuity Design and Causal Forests, we estimate heterogeneous effects conditional to farm characteristics. This approach will allow us to identify sets of farm characteristics that influence the environmental and economic efficiency of this scheme. It will enable us to revisit the question of cost-efficiency at the farm level.

3.2.5. Ex-post impact of first pillar payments on farm structural change

We propose to study the impact of first pillar CAP payments on the structural change of farms and in particular on the level of farm labour and employment, controlling for other potential confounding factors such as farm size, type of farming, legal status, farmers' age and so on.

To do so, we plan to implement the Markov chain modelling approach developed by Saint-Cyr and Piet (2017, 2019) and Saint-Cyr (2022) using FADN data to estimate the marginal effects of policy variables on transition and entry/exit probabilities, as well as on the number of farms and non-salaried and salaried agricultural workers. The main challenge will be to take account of farm entries and exits, as the FADN data do not allow these transitions to be measured directly, since farms may enter or leave the sample simply because they start or stop participating in the survey, and not necessarily because they start or stop business. The envisioned strategy is to make original use of the FADN extrapolation coefficients attached to each farm in the sample in order to deduce entry and exit flows. A difference between short-term and long-term impacts could be evidenced by estimating transition matrices over one year on the one hand, and transition matrices over, say, ten years on the other hand.

The method will first be applied to the French strand of the FADN in order to compare the results with previous studies that use other microdata sources specific to France that allow direct accounting of entries and exits (e.g. the French authority for farmer health care and social security database). Once established and validated, the method could be further applied to a selection of other Member States using their specific FADN data.

After having estimated the marginal effects of the policy variables under consideration, several scenarios involving the reallocation of a significant share of first pillar CAP payments to specific support measures, such as the complementary redistributive income support and the young farmer payment, could be studied in order to derive their potential impact on the evolution of the number of farms and workers.

3.2.6. Ex-post impact of agri-environmental schemes via production function models

We propose to study the relation between environmental subsidies and motivation of farmers in selected EU countries. The analysis is carried out using the FADN database and the micro level perspective. The motivation of farmers is based on the concept of economies of scale, scope and cost complementarities of outputs. We use the stochastic input distance models that are applied on the selected EU countries. The study hypothesized that farm agri-environmental commitments such as adoption of conservation practices generally prerequisite substantial changes in production technology and are therefore supposed to influence economies of scope and scale effects, and to impact farm practices addressing resource scarcity. That is, to better understand the determinants of structural adjustments in agriculture considering farm agri-environmental commitments and economies of scope and cost complementarities may provide evidence on the motivation of farmers to produce both environmental and marketed outputs.

3.2.7. Ex post impact of agri-environmental payments on biodiversity using remote sensing data

Our aim is twofold. First, based on the method presented in WP3, we evaluate the use of remote sensing data for arable field diversity detection in Hungary. Our second objective is to evaluate the impact of agri-environmental payments on arable land diversity in Hungary. We will use multi-year remote sensing data from Sentinel-2, which provide the possibility to detect regional variations and trends at a scale of 1:10 000.

4. EX-POST IMPACT OF THE EU TRADE POLICIES

4.1. Literature review on the existing empirical evidence

Non-tariff measures (NTMs) have gained protagonism as trade policy instruments. Firstly, because of substantial tariff cuts following multilateral and bilateral trade agreements. Secondly, regional trade and investment agreements make an increasing use of provisions on harmonisation or mutual recognition of NTMs targeted to working conditions, environmental and safety standards. Thirdly, sustainability and food standards are promoted under the auspices of the EU Green Deal. Thus, the EU's trade policy aims at improving sustainability globally by leveraging access to the EU market and ensuring EU producers compete on a level playing field (i.e. mirror clauses).

Some NTMs, as standards on sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) or technical barriers to trade (TBT), are policy instruments targeted to SJOS outcomes such as nutrition, health, food quality, sustainable production and the protection of environment. But NTMs can also affect SJOS outcomes indirectly through their influence on trade. It is a common view that compliance costs with NTMs may reduce trade, compromising the potential economic growth, and consequently affecting food security, employment, and disproportionately affect small and medium sized enterprises and women (UNCTAD, 2018; USCAP, 2019).

Most of the empirical literature on NTMs delves into the trade implications of NTMs (Ghodsi et al., 2017), and therefore, the impacts of NTMs on SJOS indicators are only implied indirectly. This section focuses on a limited number of SJOS outcomes focusing on NTMs (when possible). The objective of this review is to cover some stylized patterns found in the empirical literature on trade policy, not necessarily constrained to the EU geographical area or policy. In fact, much of the literature is concerned about SJOS impacts in less developed countries.

4.1.1. JOS Outcomes

The impact of NTMs is not necessarily gender neutral in terms of compliance costs and benefits from protection and UNCTAD (2022) provides a systematic review on empirical evidence, mainly based on case studies and anecdotal evidence. As entrepreneurs, NTMs compliance requires access to financial resources and technical skills that females lack due to education, training, time and mobility constraints, rooted in social norms. Furthermore, NTMs can be particularly burdensome for SMEs and their incidence is more spread within agrifood and textile sectors, in which there is a higher propensity for females to be employed or lead businesses. Kareem (2017) provides quantitative evidence on the widening of the gender employment gap in agriculture induced by EU SPS and TBT measures. Insufficient protection provided by inadequate technical regulations that do not account for anatomy

and physiology gender differences, on the other hand, can also affect disproportionately females engaged in high-risk production activities or as consumers of cosmetics or pharmaceutical products.

The gender impact of trade policies has been more investigated in the context of trade liberalisation, with a focus on developing countries. To the extent that females are more engaged in food sectors that have witnessed a drop in prices due to competition with increased imports, and less in cash crops benefiting from better access to international markets, the employment and wage gender gap has increased (IANWGE, 2011). Using microdata in Egypt, Zaki (2010) finds empirical support of the contribution of tariffs and procedural obstacles to gender wage disparity in Egypt.

There is an abundant literature on the impacts of trade liberalisation (through trade openness and trade and investment agreements indicators) and globalisation (economic, social and cultural, by means of the KOF index) on nutrition and health, mainly focused in low- and middle-income regions, while there is a paucity of equivalent research on the direct effect of NTMs. The review by Cuevas García-Dorado et al. (2019) points at foreign direct investment and socio-cultural aspects of globalisation as the most influential on overnutrition and prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCD) (e.g. obesity) due to the nutrition transition towards unhealthy diets. Some empirical evidence supports the positive impact of trade liberalisation to reduce undernutrition by enlarging the healthy food affordable options, while the association with NCD prevalence or overweight is not clear.

Nutrition labelling is within the spectrum of NTMs that promote healthy food choices by consumers, and ample consumer research literature supports this view (Cecchini and Warin, 2016). Likewise, Maximum Residue Levels (MRLs) requirements directly target the protection of human health (and the environment, for instance, through limits and prohibitions on pesticides), but lack of international harmonisation may impose costly trade barriers that reduces the possibilities of socio-economic development, particularly in lower income countries (Curzi et al., 2018).

Some empirical evidence suggests that adaptation of exporters to stricter standards stimulate investments and quality upgrading (Olper, Curzi and Pacca, 2014) modifying domestic supply chains (Swinnen, 2016). However, convergence to more stringent standards may divert trade away from destination markets with lower purchasing power (Disdier, Cadot and Fontagné, 2015), and may force some firms to specialise in less regulated export markets (Essaji, 2008), reducing product and markets diversification.

NTMs may also affect trade by impacting firms' export flows. As now well-established in the trade literature, firms are heterogeneous, particularly in terms of size and productivity. More productive exporters are more resilient to cost-raising NTMs than less productive ones (UNCTAD, 2018). Besides, the overall effect of NTMs on country exports may be quite ambiguous as some firms may lose, while some others may potentially benefit from the presence of NTMs in the export markets. The mechanisms at play are as follows. First, consider a NTM increasing the marginal production. Low-productive firms are likely to be harmed by this increase, and some will be excluded from the export market. Depending on the relative price impact of this industry-wide effect, incumbent firms may encounter an increase in demand. Second, suppose now that the NTM leads to a raise in fixed costs. The impact will be similar as the one previously observed, except that the effect on market structure is likely to be stronger, with a larger number of low-productive stopping their exports. In such case, and given that few firms usually account for the bulk of industry output, the NTM effect on aggregate costs of production in the industry, as well as the overall impact on exports, should be lower.

Empirical research confirms this heterogeneous effect of NTMs across firms. Relying on French firm-level customs data providing the exports per firm-product-destination and year over the period 1996-2005, Fontagné et al. (2015) highlight that big players are less impacted by NTMs than small ones, both at the extensive and intensive margins of trade. Interestingly, NTMs tend to drive the average

firm out of the market, reducing the competition between firms in the NTM-imposing market. Furthermore, multi-destination firms switch more easily toward new TBT-free destinations than mono-destination firms (Fontagné and Orefice, 2018).

A last important result deals with domestic NTMs and the ability of firms to respond to foreign demand shocks. In the presence of such a shock, firms must optimally adjust their input mix. This adjustment will be harder for firms importing inputs and facing NTMs on these imports. Consequently, these firms may observe a stronger decrease in their exports compared to firms that are not facing NTMs (Cali et al., 2022).

NTMs are also likely to affect the labour market. Mechanisms at play are well-identified in the literature. When a country enforces NTMs, such measures act as a protection from foreign competition. As a consequence, wages and employment are likely to be higher in protected sectors and lower in unprotected sectors. Consumer prices may also be impacted, and as a result, it may have implications for real wages. Similarly, when trade partners impose NTMs, this may have consequences on wages and employment in export-oriented sectors.

Thus, a removal (or harmonization/mutual recognition) of NTMs is likely to have repercussions on labour markets. Such repercussions will depend on labour market frictions and labour mobility across sectors (UNCTAD, 2018). If labour is not mobile, then only wages and employment in sectors facing NTMs are affected. At the other extreme – labour perfectly mobile across sectors – wages and employment of all workers are impacted. Finally, if labour is imperfectly mobile, wages and employment of all workers will again be impacted but at different extent. The size of the competitive shock, the degree of labour mobility and the wage differences across sectors will drive this heterogeneous impact.

4.1.2. SOS Outcomes

EU trade policies, especially non-tariff measures can have a significant impact on global and European and land conversion (Janssens et al., 2021). Williams and Kerr (2016) discuss how the EU's environmental standards for biodiesel imports can reduce land conversion in developing countries by enforcing strict sustainability and land use criteria. This approach can limit these countries' biodiesel exports to the EU, potentially decreasing land use for biofuel production and highlighting the environmental influence of EU trade policies.

Nijkamp and Vindigni (2001) examine the impact of the EU's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) on land use in Mediterranean countries. They emphasize the importance of land use planning and multi-functional land use, indicating broader effects of EU trade policies beyond agricultural production.

Grilli (1996) analyzes EU trade policies towards Less Developed Countries (LDCs), which include tariff preferences and non-tariff measures. These policies impact trade and prices of agricultural products from LDCs, influencing land use by altering the economic feasibility of certain agricultural practices.

Trabelsi (2013) investigates the impact of non-tariff measures in the Euro-Mediterranean area on agricultural trade. The findings suggest these barriers create considerable trade restrictiveness, indirectly affecting land conversion through trade flow changes and economic incentives.

Finally, Mao et al. (2023) explore the economic and environmental consequences of agricultural non-tariff measures. They observe these measures support domestic agriculture in importing countries while weakening it in exporting nations, leading to welfare distortions and increased carbon emissions from the food processing industry. This underscores the need for policy reforms to promote sustainable agri-food systems.

The relationship between trade liberalization and climate change policy has significant implications for greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, especially in agriculture. Himics et al. (2018) focus on the European Union's trade liberalization agenda, using the CAPRI model to demonstrate that while trade liberalization alone has modest effects on agricultural GHG emissions by 2030, it substantially undermines global GHG mitigation efforts when combined with carbon pricing. This is mainly due to increased emission leakage, where emission reductions within the EU are offset by increases in less emission-efficient regions. This finding highlights the complexity of formulating trade policies that balance economic and environmental sustainability, stressing the need for trade agreements to consider emission leakage to support global GHG mitigation.

Environmental provisions in Preferential Trade Agreements (PTAs) are a policy instrument that has a direct impact on environment outcomes. Several studies suggest that these provisions have been associated with lower CO₂ emissions, as shown by Francois et al. (2023) and Martinez-Zarzoso & Oueslati (2018). In addition, research by Baghdadi et al. (2013) and Zhou et al. (2017) suggests a reduction in air pollution associated with the inclusion of environmental provisions in trade agreements. While trade liberalization adds to the environmental challenges arising from trade liberalization, such as increasing deforestation (Abman & Lundberg, 2020), the inclusion of specific provisions to protect forests and biodiversity appears to offset the net increase in forest loss (Abman et al., 2021).

Pothen and Hübler (2018) and Allevi et al. (2018) show that trade policies can interact positively with environmental policies. For example, tariff removal leads to a lesser increase in emissions due to substitution and composition effects. Additionally, environmental regulations in closed-loop supply chain networks, as studied by Allevi et al. (2018), can incur additional costs for producers but ultimately reduce carbon emissions, indicating the potential for positive environmental outcomes through well-designed policies. This situation necessitates these firms' adoption of emissions reduction technologies to bridge the cost gap with developed-country firms.

The interaction between international trade policies and nutrient flows, particularly nitrogen and phosphorus, is a burgeoning area of research. However, no literature explicitly addresses the link between non-tariff measures and phosphorous/nitrate flows. Consequently, we rely on studies examining the broader impacts of trade policies. Shi et al. (2016) reveal how China's food importation, primarily from America and Asia, influences its nitrogen cycle. Nesme et al. (2016) focus on the EU's dependency on imported agricultural products and its phosphorus fertilizer footprint. Yao et al. (2021) investigate the environmental effects of US-China trade tensions on nutrient pollution.

Recent literature indicates a nuanced relationship between non-tariff measures, European trade policies, and global freshwater use and eutrophication. Hamilton et al. (2018) highlight the significant role of non-food commodities in global marine and freshwater eutrophication, influenced by income elasticity and the trade-driven nature of these impacts. This suggests the importance of expanding the focus of trade agreements and policies beyond food commodities, particularly as economies develop and consumption patterns evolve. Baylis, Nogueira, and Pace (2022) note that as tariff rates decline under WTO commitments, non-tariff measures, particularly food safety standards, emerge as significant trade impediments, as seen in the EU seafood trade where these barriers nearly offset a quarter of the gains from tariff reductions.

European Union policy initiatives such as the Green Deal (Bieroza, Bol, & Glendell, 2021) and preferential trade policies (Cipollina, Laborde Debucquet, & Salvatici, 2014; Borchert et al., 2020) play a crucial role in shaping water use and quality. Bieroza et al. (2021) critically assess the EU Green Deal, noting its potential but emphasizing the challenges in relying on the reform of the CAP for mitigating agricultural pollution. Cipollina et al. (2014) and Borchert et al. (2020) provide insights into the EU's

preferential trade policies, highlighting their significant but varied impact on trade volumes across sectors and their ability to promote trade in compliance with Non-Trade Policy Objectives. However, the limited number of studies directly linking non-tariff measures and European trade policies with freshwater use suggests an area ripe for further research.

Hirsch et al. (2020) analyze the role of water resources in foreign direct investments in land, focusing on the phenomenon of large-scale Foreign Land Acquisition (FLA). They use a gravity model to estimate the effect of agro-environmental determinants in target countries, revealing the crucial role of water resources, especially in the context of rainfed crops.

4.2. Planned empirical work to provide additional empirical evidence

4.2.1. NTM effects on trade leakage's impacts on SJOS dimensions

Task 4.2 investigates the effects of Non-Tariff Measures (NTMs) on trade dynamics and their subsequent impact on food security, land use, and biodiversity within the Sustainable Job Opportunity Structures (SJOS). Led by IIASA, this research employs a Poisson pseudo-maximum likelihood estimator to analyze zero-inflated gravity models of soybean and oil trade patterns. The study will utilize comprehensive datasets from the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) Trade Analysis Information System (TRAINS), the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAOSTAT), and the International Trade Center (BACI). The anticipated outcome is a robust database delineating trade elasticities in response to various NTMs. This will inform the refinement of the GLOBIOM trade elasticity models, enhancing our understanding of NTMs' role in shaping trade policies that reconcile economic development with environmental stewardship.

4.2.2. NTMs and trade patterns

Some NTMs, as standards on sanitary and phytosanitary (SPS) or technical barriers to trade (TBT), are policy instruments targeted to SJOS outcomes such as nutrition, health, food quality, sustainable production and the protection of environment. Moreover, NTMs can also affect SJOS outcomes indirectly through their influence on trade. In this activity, we propose to deal with both aspects. Thus, by selecting specific NTMs that promote safe (e.g. maximum residue levels) and just (e.g. nutrition labels to promote healthy choices), we aim to quantify specific trade effects for each of them. The UNCTAD TRAINS global NTM database will be used to build a panel of NTMs applied by an array of countries of relevance in international agrifood trade. Methodologically, a structural gravity equation is proposed, where alternative ways to capture specific bilateral impacts will be explored. The latter is especially relevant to quantify the particular trade effect of those NTMs imposed by the EU.

4.2.3. NTMs and sustainability issues

The EU's trade policy aims at improving sustainability globally by leveraging access to the EU market and ensuring EU producers compete on a level playing field (i.e. mirror clauses). One of the specific measures contemplated under the Green Deal to contribute to environmental sustainability is the reduction in the number of authorised pesticides and their use. This activity will initially focus on pesticides applied in agriculture. In a first stage, the EU pesticides list and restriction levels will be cross-referenced with the internationally accepted FAO-WHO Codex Alimentarius, to build a bilateral index to measure the relative stringency of EU norms against the international standards. If data availability allows, this index will be extended to contemplate pesticides application by relevant EU

trade partners. In a second stage, a structural gravity equation will be used to estimate the impact of heterogeneous pesticide use on trade patterns, with the ultimate goal of assessing if EU regulations on pesticides discourage imports from partners with less sustainable practices.

4.2.4. NTMs and International Regulatory Cooperation

Regulatory standards often impose costs which can affect international trade. Over the last decades, an increasing number of non-tariff measures (NTMs) have been notified and enforced by countries. These NTMs generally aim to address market failures related for example to consumer health or environment protection, and most of them are not protectionist per se. However, by directly or indirectly affecting the costs for producers and traders of products, as well as consumer preferences, these measures affect international trade flows and prices. International regulatory cooperation (IRC) may mitigate these negative side effects of NTMs.

This work will investigate empirically and quantify the effect of IRC mechanisms on international trade and other economic outcomes such as prices, etc. We will run macro-level (country-product level using structural gravity equations) and micro-level (firm-level relying on firm exports per product and destination for France) analyses. We aim to provide some text analysis of provisions on IRC mechanisms within preferential trade agreements. Our work will compare the effects of unilateral, supra-national (within preferential trade agreements – PTAs) and multilateral IRC mechanisms.

5. EX-POST IMPACT OF THE EU CLIMATE/ ENVIRONMENTAL POLICIES

5.1. Literature review on the existing empirical evidence

Environmental and climate policies targeted to the agricultural sector are diverse. This section focuses mostly on those that have been already implemented, to assess their ex-post impact assessment in the literature. These are: the Effort Sharing Regulation (ESR) (no. 2018/482); the Nitrates Directive (91/676/EEC) (ND); the Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC) (FWD); the National Emission reduction Commitments Directive (NECD, 2016/2284/EU); the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56/EC); the Integrated Pollution Prevention and Control Directive (IPPC, 2008/1/EG).¹

The mitigation of non-CO₂ greenhouse gases (GHG) emissions from EU agriculture (namely, methane-CH₄-and nitrous oxide-N₂O) is covered by the EU ESR, which provides for national annual emissions targets that reference the emissions of different sectors (including agriculture). MS are set free to reach their mitigation target by using different tools, including the CAP incentives of the AECM or the Eco-Schemes. As regards CO₂ emissions from Land Use, Land Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF), the related Regulation was revised in 2023. For the period 2021-2026 the revision confirms the current “no debit” rule, i.e., each MS shall ensure that accounted emissions are compensated by at least equivalent removals. Also, some national or regional initiatives exist that provide incentives for C storage in agricultural soils; these range from voluntary C (C) markets to result-based AECM schemes.

¹ IED directive: no results.

As regards the regulatory framework for an EU certification for carbon removals (COM(2022) 672 final)...
***mention that is not a regulation but it was interesting to analyse?

To this respect, to ensure high-quality EU-certified C removals, the Commission has proposed a regulatory framework for an EU certification (COM(2022) 672 final) that is now under discussion.

The ND is the core regulation to govern the use of chemical nitrogen fertilizer and manure in EU agriculture. It aims at the protection of surface and groundwater from nitrates.

The FWD generates a framework to protect groundwater and surface waters, aiming at good ecological, chemical, and quantitative status. Therefore, the WFD is an overarching regulation to protect water bodies; here we focus on its role as nutrient management policy. MS establish a program of measures for river basin districts, which include basic measures, namely other EU directives such as the ND, and supplementary measures. In the case of nutrient pollution from agriculture, the latter are largely covered by pillar II measures of the CAP. In the following, the literature analysis focuses on comprehensive analysis of the WFD which are not covered by the analysis of specific CAP policies (section 3).

Similar to the WFD and freshwater, the MSFD, 2008/56/EC generates a framework to protect marine waters and EU MS are obliged to take measures to achieve a good environmental status in the marine environment. The MSFD does not prescribe exact measures, but MS have to develop programs to reach the goals of the MSFD.

The NECD defines national emission reduction commitments for EU members states for five pollutants. Agriculture contributes by a relevant share to ammonia, non-methane volatile organic compounds, nitrogen oxides, and particulate matter (EAAE, 2023). In line with the WFD and MSFD, the NECD does not prescribe measures but defines environmental targets which MS need to reach.

The IPPC directive aims at the prevention and control of emissions from industrial activities, being relevant for agriculture in the case of intensive rearing of poultry and pigs. MS mainly define permits for industrial processes which need to reflect the Best Available Technique, addressing in the case of agriculture different forms of reactive nitrogen and phosphorus.

5.1.1. SOS Outcomes

As regard voluntary carbon markets and C credits, the only SOS dimensions covered by all the surveyed papers are biodiversity and climate change. Three studies use different types of farm financial analysis to assess break-even point for the financial viability of different C markets. In particular, two studies apply Net Present Value (NPV) analysis (Hall, 2018; De Leijester et al., 2020). Hall (2018) uses NPV to establish what carbon price would be necessary for C credits for the financial viability of a beef enterprise of 20 years duration in Estonia. With predetermined cattle revenue and carbon sequestration rates, viability evidently depends on the discount rate and C price. Leijster et al. (2020) examined the evolution of the NPV for almond farms in Spain using a stochastic cash-flow model of a number of agroecological practises (compost, green manure-GM, and no tillage-NT) in comparison to conventional tillage (CT), as well as the impact of internalising externalities through costs associated with erosion and payments for soil carbon sequestration and explore the effects of price premiums and public greening payments on farm NPV. Results point to a trade-off between income and costs from unaccounted externalities. Incentives from both public and private policies may change this result, but it would imply a significant public expenditure.²

Abdul-Salam et al. (2019) instead analyse the economic performances of alternative crop production systems when C trading markets are in place. The authors simulate the farm financial analysis of two model arable farms in the period 2011–2016 if they had each followed one of the two farm

² Despite having larger soil organic carbon stores NT and GM negligibly increased revenue through C markets. Despite CT had the highest externality costs of erosion, yet its NPV was still higher than that of NT and GM.

management systems (i.e., conventional vs. integrated) as applied to the experimental fields. The study confirms that conventional management is more profitable than a low-carbon management system even when the financial cost of GHG is considered in the framework of a C market. Only coupling an appropriate price for GHG and a premium price on products from low-carbon systems would allow to compete with conventional systems.

Other studies apply instead simulation models. Blandford et al. (2015) use a mathematical programming-price-endogenous-partial equilibrium model of Norwegian agriculture to analyse the relationship between trade liberalization and GHG emissions. The authors find that only an effective trade liberalization or a C tax could help reaching the proposed Norwegian emissions reduction (-30% in 2020 compared to 1990). However, these could negatively impact on agricultural activity; thus, only allowing for credits for C sequestration activities on land taken out of agricultural production could help keeping current aggregate production level.

Poppe et al. (2021) use the microeconomic Farmdyn model (Britz et al., 2016) to compare options for reducing GHG emissions from peat soils in Dutch agriculture. Results suggest that a pressure drainage system's technological solution may be appealing if the costs are offset, for example, by C credit payments. Results also propose an analysis of the trade-offs concerning CO₂ and NH₃ emission reductions and biodiversity.

O' Sullivan et al (2015) use a modified version of the DNDC (DeNitrification-DeComposition) model - a simulation model of carbon and nitrogen biogeochemistry in agro-ecosystems - to investigate the trade-offs between the soil functions of productivity and carbon storage in response to the use of land drainage systems for grasslands in Ireland. These trade-offs are examined in relation to the nominal cost of C credits. Results confirm that the price of CO₂ determines how these conflicting soil functions are prioritised and incentivized. The agronomic benefits outweigh the adjusted environmental costs at the present CO₂ pricing. The study also highlights large variability in environmental costs at geographical level.

The main modelling gaps of these studies are that they mostly refer to specific farm types and sizes (Hall, 2018; Abdul-Salam et al. 2019; De Leijster et al, 2020) or soil types (Poppe et al, 2021; O' Sullivan et al., 2015). Also, ecosystem service valuation, when present, can be considered controversial since it involves making assumptions about the value of ecosystem services, both monetary and non-monetary, which is subject to fluctuations in external circumstances, and is challenging, if not impossible, to value non-material ecosystem services (De Leijster et al, 2020). Modelling gaps refer also to the trade-offs in relation to the delivery of other soil functions like water purification, habitat and nutrient cycling in response to land drainage interventions (O' Sullivan et al., 2015)

The ND is directly linked to the safe space dimension of biogeochemical flows. Existing literature focuses on ex-post monitoring of nitrates concentration in ground and surface water in case study settings and partly links it to the measures of the ND (Gomes et al., 2023; Hooda et al., 1997; Lagzdins et al., 2015; van Grinsven et al., 2012). Such monitoring activities are also part of the frequent reports by the MS to the EU Commission on their implementation of the ND. In addition, indicators for nitrogen losses such as nitrogen balances are estimated at different scale and related to ND measures (Buckley et al., 2016a; Cameira et al., 2019; van Grinsven et al., 2012).

Modelling at field, farm, catchment, and regional scale is mainly used for ex-ante evaluation of measures of the ND on nitrogen emissions (Ackermann et al., 2016; Belhouchette et al., 2011; Berentsen and Tiessink, 2003; Costa et al., 2021; Koos et al., 2021; Oenema et al., 2009; Wilk et al., 2019; Wolf et al., 2003) or for ex-post simulations where empirical observations are challenging (Motarjemi et al., 2021; van Calster et al., 2004). Research on the ND partially also covers phosphorus emissions (Buckley et al., 2016b; McDonald et al., 2019) as the ND implementation in members states often addresses both nutrients. Generally, existing research mainly provides case study results for a catchment or a region, reflecting the diverse implementation of the ND in MS. Cross-country

comparisons and EU wide analysis are rare (Oenema et al., 2009; van Grinsven et al., 2012), but valuable for understanding the impact of specific measures and a general evaluation of the ND.

Little research is present on possible synergies and trade-offs between the ND and other safe space dimensions beyond biogeochemical flows. However, the ND is clearly related to climate change, biosphere integrity, and aerosol loading. The MS' implementation also foresees an environmental impact assessment, following the EU directive on the assessment of the effects of certain public and private projects on the environment (2011/92/EU), which covers environmental impacts beyond biogeochemical flows (see for example German revision at BMEL, 2016). Empirical research hints for instance at the link between buffer strips provided for surface water quality and biodiversity (Izydorczyk et al., 2018) and linkage between reduced N inputs and lower measured nitrous oxide emissions (Cocco et al., 2018). Generally, model analyses provide more frequently the impact of the ND measures on various safe space indicators (Belhouchette et al., 2011; Oenema et al., 2009; Prado and Scholefield, 2008; van Calker et al., 2004) and also address the possible trade-off between different environmental goals (Paterson and Holden, 2019; Splinter and Peerlings, 2023). However, ex-post estimations of the impacts of the ND on other safe dimensions are rare but crucial for a broader understanding of policy impacts. They need to cover amongst other the impact on climate change due to changes of N₂O emissions and the impact on ammonia emissions, being linked to terrestrial biodiversity via exceeding critical nitrogen loads and the formation of aerosols.

As regards the MSFD in relation to agriculture, bio-geochemical flows are the most relevant safe dimension but also other dimensions such as biosphere integrity or novel entities are of interest. Measures against eutrophication are evaluated in terms of descriptors of the MSFD in ex-ante modelling (Ackermann et al., 2016; Friedland et al., 2021; Grizzetti et al., 2021) but assessments of measures specific to the MSFD in the action plans of MS are missing. Finally, little research is found on impacts of the MSFD in relation to agriculture. This is due to the fact that most relevant measures are part of other EU policies, such as the ND and CAP (Salomon and Dross, 2013), and their implementation in MS.

The NECD is directly linked to the safe dimensions of bio-geochemical flows, biosphere integrity, ozone depletion and aerosol loading. Ex-post analysis link the NECD to calculated emission inventories (van Grinsven et al., 2016, 2015) which are also covered by compulsory reporting of the MS. The majority of research are ex-ante assessments for the analysis of measures and scenarios to meet the ceilings of the NECD at different scales (Ferreira et al., 2017; Hu and Schmidhalter, 2021; Lumbreras et al., 2008; Mircea et al., 2015; van Grinsven et al., 2015). Ex-post and ex-ante assessments also go beyond the calculation of air pollutants and estimate actual impacts, such as nitrogen deposition in the Baltic sea (Gauss et al., 2021), critical load exceedance (Hettelingh and Posch, 2019) and health impacts (Giannakis et al., 2019), as well as use monitoring data (De Marco et al., 2019; Serrano et al., 2019; van Grinsven et al., 2016).

The IPPC directive is directly linked to the safe dimension of bio-geochemical flows as well as aerosol loading and biosphere integrity. The implementation of the directive in MS is a crucial measure to meet emission ceilings under the NECD. Little research exists on the impacts of the IPPC directive on relevant safe dimensions. Ex-ante modelling at different scale is conducted to assess the emission reduction (Pellini and Morris, 2001; Webb et al., 2006), partly also relating emissions to actual impacts (Angus et al., 2006). Cross-country comparisons only exists in a qualitative way (Kunes et al., 2022) as well as an older review of measures under the IPPC directive (Loyon et al., 2016). There is no literature found on the emission or impact reduction of the directive on a country or EU scale or on synergies and trade-offs with safe dimensions besides the targeted emissions. However, the impacts of the IPPC directive on relevant emissions are reflected in the reporting of MS under e.g., the NECD.

5.1.2. JOS Outcomes

As regards the C markets, the only dimension covered is the one on income and labour.³ Indeed, all works analyse impacts on farms viability, but only three works address the issue explicitly. In particular Poppe et al. (2021) show estimates of farm income losses for three different changes in water levels in peat soils associated with changes in production methods for three options of NH₃ emission reductions and three options for nature conservation areas, showing that giving a value to C credits could obviously help reducing these income losses. De Leijster et al. (2020) analyse the trade-offs between income losses and environmental externalities generate, while and O'Sullivan et al. (2015) show that the environmental costs do not translate into a change in farmers' income, in presence of a C price. Modelling gaps include the analysis of trade-offs with the other dimensions of the JUST operating space.

Regarding the just space, little is known also on the impacts of the ND. Mainly farm income is addressed in modelling studies, estimating on-farm compliance costs or income change with bio-economic farm models (Belhouchette et al., 2011; Berentsen and Tiessink, 2003; Kuhn et al., 2019; Pahmeyer et al., 2021; van Calker et al., 2004) or sectoral economic indicators with large-scale models (Oenema et al., 2009). Ex-post empirical work of past ND implementation on farm income or further just dimension is needed. The impact of fertilizer restrictions as part of the ND are evaluated in field trials with respect to yield, quality, and economic implications (Pirko et al., 2020; Szafranska et al., 2023), also indicating possible impacts on the food dimension. However, a comprehensive analysis of yield and market effects of the ND, going beyond the field level and single ND measures, is missing.

About the MSFD, no research is found on the just dimension.

The NECD addresses air pollutants and is therefore directly linked to the just dimension of health. A body of literature related to air quality changes and health impacts exists, partly also opposing health benefits and costs (Giannakis et al., 2019; Piersanti et al., 2021; Schucht et al., 2018; van Grinsven et al., 2016). The inclusion of the costs of measures also addresses the income dimensions, research on the NECD with regard to other just dimensions is missing. As with the MSFD and WFD, other EU and national policies prescribe the actual measures to meet the NECD directive and are subject to research, allowing also conclusion for the NECD.

Existing research on the IPPC directive also includes the assessment of abatement costs and cost-efficiency of measures (Angus et al., 2006; Webb et al., 2006), given hints at the impacts on the income dimension. Though, more comprehensive research on income effects of the IPPC directive as well as other just dimensions is missing.

5.2. Planned empirical work to provide additional empirical evidence

5.2.1. Ex-post evaluation of climate-related payment schemes via ML techniques

The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) has long transformed into a set of instruments designed to incrementally address the environmental and ecological concerns that the EU farming system have raised across several decades. Giving the high priority of these topics in the current political agendas,

³ Hall (2018) slightly addresses gender issues, by stressing that the C credit rewarding system presented could easily be applied within a policy framework aimed at gender equity.

this subtask tackles the heterogeneous causal effect of the EU climate and environmental policy tools. To pursue this goal, we exploit a mix of data fusion techniques to incorporate GHG emission information in the EU FADN data and Double Machine Learning methods to identify and compute the heterogeneous policy responses. The methodology used to calculate GHG emissions at micro level is based on the adaptation at farm level of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change method (IPCC 2006). According to this approach, the computation of GHG emissions relies on a linear relationship between emission factors (EF) and activity data (AD). EF derive from the Italian national GHG reporting system (ISPRA, 2019) and AD are taken from FADN dataset for each source of emission. The methodology estimates emission from the following sources: CH₄ from manure management, enteric fermentation and rice cultivation; N₂O from manure management, use of synthetic fertilisers, manure application, crop residues, animal production and related indirect emission, and CO₂ from energy consumption (both electricity and fuel). This approach was based on the conceptual framework proposed by Coderoni and Esposti (2018) and further develop by Coderoni and Vanino (2022). The intended outcome of this subtask is a scientific publication to be drafted by the leading team (UCSC), possibly cooperating with other partners to be defined.

5.2.2. Ex-post evaluation of agri-environmental policies on crop choices

This research addresses if and how farmers adapt their crop choices in response to agri-environmental policies. Such knowledge is amongst other crucial to detect unintended consequences of policies and estimate compliance costs for farmers. We use a Bayesian probabilistic programming approach and spatial explicit field data from the Integrated Administration and Control System (IACS). More specifically, we plan to apply a multi-level model that allows for individual field-level intercepts (similar to a fixed-effects model) while estimating an adaptive prior for those intercepts at the regional level. The revised German implementation of the EU Nitrates Directive, which has undergone fundamental changes over the last few years, is researched. So-called red areas, where high nitrate concentration in groundwater bodies is found, were introduced alongside additional restrictions for fertilizing activities. Farmers are likely reacting by changing management, such as adapting fertilizer amounts or crop rotations. The developed methodology can, however, be applied to other spatial differentiated policies that may impact crop choices, such as pesticide use restrictions in protected areas or management restrictions in water protection areas. Furthermore, the generated knowledge can, for example, be used by farm modelling activities to correctly capture policy responses in the model and validate results.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this preliminary deliverable we have carried out a systematic review of the literature on the relationships between some key public policies affecting agricultural and food and the SJOS dimensions. In general, our results show that the available evidence is somehow scattered across the SJOS thematic areas, with a clear prevalence of the environmental (SOS) with respect to the social (JOS) ones. Thus, there is a clear research gap in exploring the impact of public policies on JOS issues such as social equity, health and nutrition security. Moreover, very few studies explore synergies and trade-offs between different SJOS dimensions. This is especially relevant if one wishes to evaluate a complex policy mix such as the Green Deal of the EU. Finally, from a methodological perspective, the available studies provide some interesting hints for extending the available toolkit for ex-ante policy modelling, which deserve further research.

In addition to the literature review, we have provided a description of the activities that we are planning to carry out during the time span of Work Package 4 (ending in month 36 of the project), emphasising their potential contribution to the modelling activities that are carried out in other WPs.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This document was produced under the terms and conditions of Grant Agreement No. 101060075 for the European Commission. It does not necessary reflect the view of the European Union and in no way anticipates the Commission's future policy in this area.

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